

FLOW-INDUCED ALIGNMENT OF FIBERS

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SUMMARY: The temporal response of a fiber suspension subjected to a homogeneous shear field is examined by solving a closed evolution equation for the second-order moment $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ of the orientation distribution function. The dyadic-valued moment equation is integrated from three different initial states: isotropic, planar isotropic, and uniaxially aligned. For all cases, the suspension relaxes to a unique orientation state parameterized by a fiber/fiber interaction coefficient. All the instantaneous states predicted by the theory are physically realizable inasmuch as the eigenvalues of the orientation dyadic are non-negative. Closure of the moment equation is achieved by using an approximate model for the orientation tetradic $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ that preserves the six-fold symmetry and contraction properties of the exact tetradic operator. The calculations compare favorably with the temporal response of the orientation dyadic calculated directly from the fiber orientation distribution function.

KEYWORDS: fiber alignment, orientation distribution function, orientation dyadic, orientation tetradic, realizability, fiber/fluid interactions, fiber/fiber interactions, closure approximation, homogeneous shear

INTRODUCTION

Flow-induced alignment of chopped-fibers during processing provides a practical and relatively inexpensive means to control the microstructure of fiber reinforced polymeric and ceramic materials [1]. This is important because the rheological response of fiber-fluid suspensions and the mechanical response of chopped-fiber composites are closely linked to the microstructure associated with the fiber orientation states [2].

The microstructure is often characterized by the second-order and fourth-order moments of the fiber orientation distribution function [3]:

$$\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \mathbf{pp} \Psi(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{x}, t) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi \quad (1)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \mathbf{pppp} \Psi(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{x}, t) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi \quad (2)$$

where $\Psi(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{x}, t) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi$ represents the fraction of fibers with orientation vectors between \mathbf{p} and $\mathbf{p}+\Delta\mathbf{p}$. The fiber orientation distribution function satisfies the following continuity equation in orientation space [3]:

$$\frac{D\Psi}{Dt} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \cdot (\dot{\mathbf{p}}\Psi). \quad (3)$$

In the above equation, $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$ represents the rotational (or angular) velocity of the fiber; thus, $\mathbf{p} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}} = 0$ and $\|\mathbf{p}\| = \text{constant}$. $D\Psi/Dt$ is the substantial derivative of the orientation distribution function, $\partial\Psi/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla\Psi$. \mathbf{u} is the velocity of a material point located at the centroid of a neutrally buoyant fiber. The mass average velocity of the fiber/fluid suspension and the linear velocity of the fiber are equal. The differential operator $\partial/\partial \mathbf{p}$ is defined as $(\underline{\mathbf{I}} - \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}) \cdot \nabla$. The rotational flux $\dot{\mathbf{p}}\Psi$ in Eqn 3 has two significant contributions: 1) a rotary convective contribution, $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J\Psi$, due to *fiber-fluid interactions*; and, 2) a rotary diffusive contribution, $(\dot{\mathbf{p}} - \dot{\mathbf{p}}_J)\Psi$, due to *fiber-fiber interactions*. An expression for the rotational velocity $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J$ was originally developed by Jeffrey [4] for rigid ellipsoidal particles suspended in a Newtonian fluid. This theory gives the following result for neutrally buoyant, rigid fibers:

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{W}}}^T \cdot \mathbf{p} + \lambda(\underline{\mathbf{I}} - \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}) \cdot (\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \cdot \mathbf{p}). \quad (4)$$

In the above equation, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{W}}}$ represent, resp., the symmetric and antisymmetric components of the velocity gradient imposed on the suspension. The fiber-fluid coupling coefficient λ is defined as

$$\lambda \equiv \frac{\alpha^2 - 1}{\alpha^2 + 1} \quad (5)$$

where α is an equivalent aspect ratio for cylindrical fibers, $\alpha = (L/D)_e$. For a sphere, $\lambda = 0$ and $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J$ equals the angular velocity of the suspension. For chopped fibers used in composites, $\alpha > 1$ and the rate-of-strain dyadic $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}$ as well as the vorticity dyadic $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{W}}}$ influence $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J$ significantly. Equation 4 implies that \mathbf{p} and $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J$ are orthogonal vectors (*i.e.*, $\mathbf{p} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}_J = 0$) for all flows.

The rotary diffusive contribution to $\dot{\mathbf{p}}\Psi$ stems from a stochastic process related to fiber-fiber interactions [5]:

$$(\dot{\mathbf{p}} - \dot{\mathbf{p}}_J)\Psi = -D_R \frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial \mathbf{p}}. \quad (6)$$

For very dilute suspensions, the rotary diffusion coefficient D_R approaches zero and the rotational flux $\dot{\mathbf{p}}\Psi$ reduces to $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_J\Psi$. Folgar and Tucker [6] have argued that D_R should depend on the local strain rate of the suspension and suggested that

$$D_R = C_I(\phi_f) \sqrt{2\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}}. \quad (7)$$

The dimensionless fiber-fiber interaction coefficient $C_I(\phi_f)$ is an empirical function of the volume fraction of the dispersed fiber phase. Eqn 7 implies that the steady state orientation distribution function does not depend on the magnitude of the velocity gradient for simple shear flows. If $\|\nabla \underline{\mathbf{u}}\| = 0$, Eqn 4 and Eqn 7 imply that $\dot{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{0}$, instantaneously. Unlike Brownian

diffusion, the foregoing model does not relax to an isotropic orientation once the hydrodynamic forces are removed.

SECOND-ORDER MOMENT EQUATION

An evolution equation for the orientation dyadic $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ follows by multiplying Eqn 3 by the dyad \mathbf{pp} and integrating over the surface of a sphere. With $\underline{\mathbf{a}} \equiv \langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ and $\underline{\mathbf{p}}$ defined by Eqns 4 and 6, the foregoing analysis yields the following result [7,8]:

$$\frac{D\underline{\mathbf{a}}}{Dt} + \underline{\mathbf{W}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{W}}^T = \lambda [\underline{\mathbf{S}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{S}} - 2\underline{\mathbf{M}}] + 2 D_r [\underline{\mathbf{I}} - 3\underline{\mathbf{a}}], \quad (8)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{M}} \equiv \langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle : \underline{\mathbf{S}}. \quad (9)$$

The left-hand-side of Eqn 8 is the Jaumann derivative of the orientation dyadic [2]. $\underline{\mathbf{M}}$ is symmetric and must satisfy the following contraction property

$$\text{tr}(\underline{\mathbf{M}}) = \underline{\mathbf{a}} : \underline{\mathbf{S}}. \quad (10)$$

Thus, Eqn 8 preserves two fundamental properties of the orientation dyadic, *viz.*, $\underline{\mathbf{a}} = \underline{\mathbf{a}}^T$ and $\text{tr}(\underline{\mathbf{a}}) = 1$.

The orientation *tetradic* operator $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ is unchanged by a formal exchange (transpose) of any two orientation vectors. This means that any approximate representation for $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ should satisfy the following six *symmetry operations*

$$\begin{aligned} \langle p_i p_j p_k p_l \rangle &= \langle p_j p_i p_k p_l \rangle = \langle p_k p_j p_i p_l \rangle \\ &= \langle p_i p_j p_k p_i \rangle = \langle p_i p_k p_j p_i \rangle \\ &= \langle p_i p_i p_k p_j \rangle = \langle p_i p_j p_i p_k \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The normalization condition $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = 1$ requires that a contraction between any two orientation vectors in $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ gives the orientation dyadic exactly. Thus, an approximate representation for $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ should also satisfy the following six *projection operations* (sum over s)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle p_i p_j \rangle &= \langle p_s p_s p_i p_j \rangle = \langle p_s p_i p_s p_j \rangle \\ &= \langle p_s p_i p_j p_s \rangle = \langle p_i p_s p_s p_j \rangle \\ &= \langle p_i p_s p_j p_s \rangle = \langle p_i p_j p_s p_s \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Cintra and Tucker [9] as well as Dupret *et al.* [10] have recently developed closure approximations which implicitly retain all the conditions expressed by Eqn 11 and Eqn 12. These properties are also retained in the closure approximation used hereinafter. However, unlike the two previous studies, a class of closure approximations have been identified that gives a closed-form explicit representation of the orientation tetradic in terms of the orientation dyadic.

Because $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}^T$, the eigenvalues of the orientation dyadic $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ are real. Furthermore, because $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ is also the average of a dyad (*i.e.*, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} = \langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle$), the eigenvalues of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ are non-negative; therefore, any approximate closure model for $\langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle$ must preserve this important *realizability* property of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ (see Ref 11).

Figure 1. Realizable response to simple shear for $\lambda = 1$ and $C_I = 0.01$ for uniaxial (A), planar (B), and isotropic (C) initial distributions (\square : Ref. 9; — : This research, $C_2 = 1/3$).

Realizability of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ can be expressed in terms of the invariants of the anisotropic orientation dyadic defined as follows

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}} \equiv \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} - \frac{1}{3} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}. \quad (13)$$

Because $\text{tr}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}) = 1$, the first invariant of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}$ (*i.e.*, $I_b \equiv \text{tr}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}})$) is zero for all orientation states. However, the second and third invariants, defined as

$$II_b \equiv \text{tr}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}) \quad \text{and} \quad III_b \equiv \text{tr}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}), \quad (14)$$

are generally non-zero and are bounded by the closed region illustrated by Figure 1 (cf. Ref. 11). Alternatively, Cintra and Tucker [9] use the two largest eigenvalues of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ to parameterize the set of bounded *realizable* orientation states, rather than the anisotropic invariants defined by Eqn 14. An anisotropic orientation state (II_b, III_b) outside the *realizable* set implies that at least one of the

eigenvalues associated with $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ is negative, which is an unacceptable result for any approximate orientation model. The three corners of the invariant diagram correspond to uniaxial alignments (point A), planar isotropic orientations (point B), and isotropic orientations. The locus of boundary states between points A and B correspond to planar anisotropic states; the boundary points between B and C are planar axisymmetric states; and, the boundary points between C and A correspond to axial axisymmetric orientation states.

CLOSURE APPROXIMATIONS

Equation 8 requires a closure model for the orientation tetradic $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$. A commonly employed hypothesis [12] is that $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ is determined by the local value of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$:

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle = \mathfrak{S}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}). \quad (15)$$

As noted by Hand [7], Cintra and Tucker [9], Dupret *et al.* [10] and many others, the Cayley-Hamilton theorem [13] implies that a closed form representation of Eqn 15 will involve scalar-valued functions of the invariants of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ (or, equivalently, the invariants II_b and III_b) and the symmetric forms of six tetradic operators. The idea underlying the new closure approximation employed hereinafter is to express $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ as the sum of four *irreducible* tetrads that individually satisfy all the symmetry conditions given by Eqn 11:

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^4 C_n \langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_n. \quad (16)$$

Equation 16 generalizes the *ad hoc* hybrid closure approximation used by Advani and Tucker [12]. Each tetradic operator $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_n$ in Eqn 16 has a different dependence on $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$. With $n=1$, a first-order dependence on the orientation dyadic is indicated

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_1 = \frac{1}{7} S(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}) - \frac{1}{35} S(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}). \quad (17)$$

Eqn 17 has the same symmetry and projection properties as $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ and was used earlier by Hand [7] as a model for $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ for nearly isotropic orientations (*i.e.*, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} \rightarrow \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}/3$). For symmetric dyads $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}$, the tetradic operator $S(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}})$ is defined as

$$S(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}) = A_{ij}B_{kl} + A_{ik}B_{jl} + A_{il}B_{kj} + B_{ij}A_{kl} + B_{ik}A_{jl} + B_{il}A_{kj}. \quad (18)$$

If $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}$ are the same, then the symmetric operator $S(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}})$ is defined by

$$S(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}) = A_{ij}A_{kl} + A_{ik}A_{jl} + A_{il}A_{kj}. \quad (19)$$

The other tetrads in Eqn 16 are defined by the following representation

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_n = \sum_{m=1}^8 \alpha_{nm} \mathfrak{K}_m, \quad (20)$$

Table 1. Component Tetradic Operators

m	\mathfrak{K}_m
1	$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}]$
2	$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}]$
3	$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}]$
4	$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})]$
5	$S[(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}]$
6	$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})]$
7	$S[(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})]$
8	$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})]$

where the component tetradic operators \mathfrak{K}_m are defined in terms of the symmetry operators S (see Table 1). The scalar coefficients α_{nm} , which depend on the invariants of the orientation dyadic, are defined by Table 2. Clearly, the Cayley-Hamilton theorem [13] could be used to eliminate the $m = 6$ and the $m = 8$ terms in Eqn 20.

It is noteworthy that all of the tetradic operators $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_n$ satisfy Eqn 11. Furthermore, the first three tetrads have the same projection properties as $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$. However, the contraction between any two vectors in $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_4$ gives the second-order null operator. For example,

$$\sum_i \langle \mathbf{p}_i \mathbf{p}_i \mathbf{pp} \rangle_4 = \sum_i \langle \mathbf{p}_i \mathbf{pp} \mathbf{p}_i \rangle_4 = \dots = \sum_i \langle \mathbf{p}_i \mathbf{ppp} \mathbf{p}_i \rangle_4 = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{O}}}. \quad (21)$$

Thus, the foregoing orientation tetradic operator satisfies the symmetry properties given by Eqn 11 and the projection properties given by Eqn 12 provided

$$\sum_{n=1}^3 C_n = 1. \quad (22)$$

Table 2. Expansion Coefficients

n	α_{nm}							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	$-\frac{1}{35}$	$\frac{1}{7}$	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	$\frac{2}{35} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}:\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$	0	1	$-\frac{2}{7}$	0	0	0	0
3	$\frac{1}{35} + \frac{4}{35} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}:(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})^{-1}$	0	0	$-\frac{1}{7}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})^{-1}$	$(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})^{-1}$	$-\frac{4}{7}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})^{-1}$	0	0
4	$\frac{2}{35}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}):(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}) + \frac{1}{35}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})^2$	0	0	$-\frac{1}{7}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\cdot\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})$	0	0	1	$-\frac{2}{7}$

The scalar-valued weighting factors C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 are unspecified functions of the anisotropic invariants Π_b and III_b . The theory approaches the linear model of Hand [7] as the orientation states become isotropic (*i.e.*, $\Pi_b \rightarrow 0$ and $\text{III}_b \rightarrow 0$) if $(C_2, C_3, C_4) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0)$. On the other hand, $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ approaches the second-order approximation $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2$ as the orientation states become highly aligned (*i.e.*, $\Pi_b \rightarrow 2/3$ and $\text{III}_b \rightarrow 2/9$) if $(C_2, C_3, C_4) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0)$. Comparing the solutions of Eqn 8 and Eqn 3 for simple shear flows can identify additional restrictions on C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 . Cintra and Tucker [9] used this self-consistent approach to evaluate the efficacy of an *orthotropic closure approximation*. This strategy will also be used hereinafter.

Here the following tetradic closure, which is a special case of Eqn 16, will be employed to estimate the second-order moment governed by Eqn 8:

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle = (1-C_2)\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_1 + C_2\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2 . \quad (23)$$

$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_1$ is defined by Eqn 17 and

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2 = \frac{2}{35} \mathbf{a} : \mathbf{a} \mathbf{S}[\mathbf{II}] + \mathbf{S}[\mathbf{aa}] - \frac{2}{7} \mathbf{S}[\mathbf{Ia} \cdot \mathbf{a}] . \quad (24)$$

Instead of Eqn 24, Advani and Tucker [12] used the following approximation for the second component of the orientation tetradic: $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2 \cong \mathbf{aa}$. They also used the following *ad hoc* expression for the weighting factor: $C_2 = 1 - 27\det(\mathbf{a})$. Note that as $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{I}/3$, $C_2 \rightarrow 0$; and, as $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_3$, $C_2 \rightarrow 1$. This hybrid model, *albeit* simple, unfortunately does not satisfy all the symmetry conditions and projection operations of the exact orientation tetradic. Nevertheless, it may still provide a good qualitative approximation for a limited class of engineering flows provided it predicts non-negative eigenvalues for the orientation dyadic.

With $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ defined by Eqn 23, the normalization operator \mathbf{M} in Eqn 8 can be written as

$$\mathbf{M} = (1 - C_2) \mathbf{M}_1 + C_2 \mathbf{M}_2 \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_1 \equiv -\frac{2}{35} \mathbf{S} + \frac{1}{7} [\mathbf{a} : \mathbf{S} \mathbf{I} + 2 \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{a} + 2 \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{S}] \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_2 \equiv \mathbf{a} : \mathbf{S} \mathbf{a} + 2 \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{a} + \frac{4}{35} \mathbf{a} : \mathbf{a} \mathbf{S} - \frac{2}{7} [(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a}) : \mathbf{S} \mathbf{I} + 2 \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a} + 2 \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{S}] . \quad (27)$$

The efficacy of the hybrid model defined by Eqns 25-27 is examined for a class of homogeneous shear flows in the next section. For the calculations presented hereinafter, the fiber/fluid interaction parameter $\lambda = 1$, and the fiber/fiber interaction parameter $C_1 = 0.01$. Calculations for other flows and conditions will be presented elsewhere. The tetradic weighting factor C_2 , unlike the Advani and Tucker model described above, is presumed to be a constant for all orientation states.

FIBER ORIENTATION STATISTICS: SIMPLE SHEAR FLOWS

For simple shear flows, the fluid velocity has a single component that varies linearly across the flow domain. With $\dot{\gamma} \equiv du_3/dx_2$, \mathbf{S} and the vorticity dyadic \mathbf{W} can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{\dot{\gamma}}{2} (\mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_2) \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \frac{\dot{\gamma}}{2} (\mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_3 - \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_2) \quad (29)$$

Eqn 8 simplifies significantly for $\underline{\mathbf{S}}$ and $\underline{\mathbf{W}}$ given by Eqns 28 and 29, respectively. For example, the rotary diffusion coefficient, defined by Eqn 7, reduces to $D_R = \dot{\gamma} C_1(\phi_f)$ and the steady state orientation dyadic $\underline{\mathbf{a}}$ has only five nontrivial components:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \underline{\mathbf{a}} = a_{11} \mathbf{e}_1 \mathbf{e}_1 + a_{22} \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_2 + a_{33} \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_3 + a_{23} \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_3 + a_{32} \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_2 \quad (30)$$

Because $\underline{\mathbf{a}} = \underline{\mathbf{a}}^T$ and $tr(\underline{\mathbf{a}}) = 1$, $a_{23} = a_{32}$ and $a_{11} = 1 - a_{22} - a_{33}$. Eqn 30 also holds instantaneously, if the initial state is characterized by $a_{12}(0) = a_{13}(0) = 0$.

Figure 2. Transient response of an initially isotropic distribution to simple shear for $\lambda = 1$ and $C_1 = 0.01$ (\square : Ref. 9; - - -: Ref. 12; — : This research, $C_2 = 1/3$).

Figure 3. Transient response of initially anisotropic distributions to simple shear for $\lambda = 1$, $C_1 = 0.01$, and $C_2 = 1/3$.

Figure 2 shows the temporal behavior of the components of $\underline{\mathbf{a}}$ in a frame of reference moving with the local fluid velocity. The independent variable time has been scaled with the characteristic strain rate $\dot{\gamma}$, so $\tau = \dot{\gamma} t$. Eqn 8 was solved for a fiber/fluid interaction parameter $\lambda = 1$, a fiber/fiber interaction parameter $C_1 = 0.01$, and a tetradic weighting factor $C_2 = 1/3$. A fourth-order Runge-Kutta algorithm [14] was used to integrate the non-linear coupled set of equations subject to an isotropic initial condition: $\underline{\mathbf{a}}(0) = \underline{\mathbf{I}}/3$ (i.e., $\text{II}_b = 0$ and $\text{III}_b = 0$).

Figure 2 also shows the components of $\underline{\mathbf{a}}$ previously calculated by Cintra and Tucker [9] based on a direct numerical solution of Eqn 3, which requires no closure approximation. The tetradic weighting factor C_2 was selected to closely approximate the steady orientation state predicted by the orientation distribution function for $C_1 = 0.01$. The close agreement between the dynamic response of the second-order moment model and the exact results based on Eqn 3 partially supports the conjecture that C_2 is approximately independent of the local orientation state. The instantaneous values of the invariants of the anisotropic orientation dyadic $\underline{\mathbf{b}}$ for this calculation are shown on Figure 1.

The component a_{33} on Figure 2 designated Advani & Tucker [12] was calculated by using the widely used model $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2 = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$, instead of Eqn 24. As previously mentioned, although this hybrid model does not satisfy all the symmetry and contraction properties expressed by Eqns 11 and 12, it nevertheless predicts realizable orientation states.

Figure 3 shows the temporal response of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}$ for an initially uniaxially aligned orientation state: $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}(0) = \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_3$; and, an initially isotropic planar state: $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}(0) = (\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_2 + \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_3)/2$. Eqn 8 was solved for these initial conditions with $\lambda = 1$, $C_1 = 0.01$, and $C_2 = 1/3$. Figure 1 also shows the locus of instantaneous anisotropic invariants associated with these calculations.

CONCLUSIONS

Equations 16 and 20, together with Tables 1 and 2, define a new closure approximation for the orientation tetradic that retains all six symmetry and projection operations expressed by Eqns 11 and 12. The theory generalizes an earlier closure approximation introduced by Hand [7] for nearly isotropic orientations to include highly anisotropic states such as uniaxially aligned and planar isotropic configurations.

Equation 23, which is a special case of the more general theory presented herein, is used to examine the temporal response of the orientation dyadic to a homogeneous simple shear field. Figure 1 shows that all three extreme initial conditions relax to a unique steady orientation state for $\tau \gg 20$. In as much as the instantaneous orientation states are all within the anisotropic invariant diagram (see Figure 1), the eigenvalues of the orientation dyadic are non-negative for these calculations. Thus, the second-order moment model defined by Eqn 8 and Eqn 25 is realizable; unfortunately, this does not necessarily imply that the reduced theory (i.e., $C_3 = C_4 = 0$ in Eqn 16) is realizable for other flows or initial conditions. This important topic will be addressed more generally elsewhere.

Equation 8 and Eqn 25 reproduce the details of the relaxation process from an initially isotropic state predicted by the direct numerical solution to Eqn 3 (see Figure 2). This result partially justifies the use of a tetradic weighting factor in Eqn 25 that does not depend on the local orientation state (i.e., $C_2 = 1/3$). During the initial stage of the relaxation process from an isotropic state, the fiber/fluid interactions induce a cross correlation between fibers oriented in the flow and cross-flow directions ($a_{23} > 0$). Fiber/fiber interactions accounted for by the rotary diffusion phenomena become significant during the final stages of the temporal response as the anisotropic component of the orientation dyadic develops. Note, however, that the relaxation of the orientation dyadic from an uniaxial-aligned state is controlled by rotary diffusion rather than fiber/fluid interactions during the initial stage. As illustrated by the expanded region surrounding the final steady state, a complex response occurs during the final stage when fiber/fluid interactions begin to moderate the initial fiber/fiber response.

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